

ROLE OF SOCIAL-HISTORICAL CONDITIONS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF POETIC THOUGHT (A CASE STUDY OF THE CREATION OF TULAGAN KHOZHAMYROV TAVALLO)

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Annotation

This article discusses the role of the author's artistic thought in the creation of a literary work. Employing examples, it analyzes the socio-historical conditions, the impact of past events on the creator, and the significance of this influence in the process of artistic creation.

Key words

Jadidism, modern period literature, Uzbek literature, Tavallo, poetic reflection, socio-historical conditions, image, depiction.

The social-historical conditions of the second half of the 19th century profoundly transformed Uzbek literature in the early 20th century. During this period, the national revival movement began not only in Turkestan but also in many colonies around the world. It became evident that achieving progress was impossible without awakening the nation from ignorance and fostering a collective aspiration for development in the spirit of the people.

Enlightened individuals transformed literature into a tool to combat ignorance and a weapon for salvation from colonial oppression, as advocated by the Jadids. Writers aligned with the Jadid movement, including Tavallo, sought to awaken the nation, and, as noted, they "attempted to express new themes through new images" [1: 183]. The necessity to articulate ideas through artistic works surged. "The ancients transformed the centuries-old Uzbek poetry from melody to prayer" [1: 184].

The conditions of colonialism, discrimination against the nation by the Russians, and factors inevitably leading to illiteracy shaped a distinct imagery and theme in Tavallo's creative output.

It is pertinent to note that against the backdrop of socio-historical events, in the works of Tavallo, contrary to previous motifs, one can encounter poems imbued with the spirit of the First World War, mobilization events, and the October Revolution.

**Siza yangi hukumat bas, musallam taxtga miningiz,
Adolat masnadida bir Xudo pushti panohingiz,**

**Zumurrad, la'l, yoqut toj bosh uzra kulohingiz,
Hamisha sidqi ixlos ila bizlar uzrxohingiz,
Tavallo ayladik dargohi Haqq'a biz musulmonlar,
Vatanga hamwatanmiz deb biling emdi, slavyanlar [2:155],**

The Russian Empire in the events of the First World War, which took place from 1914 to 1918. It also mentions the policy of Oqposhsho (an Uzbek term, context needed for precise translation) and addresses General-Adjutant A. N. Kuropatkin.

**Xush kelibsiz shahrimizga, ey ulug' oliy maqom,
Siz adolat taxti uzra o'ltiring, bizdir g'ulom.
Taxti davlat, taxti izzat, fathi nusrat biz tilab
Uxlamasmiz yolborib, avlod bizlar subhu shom,**

He said, From these lines, one might suspect that Tavallo was a supporter of the imperial government. However, some time later, in 1925, he published a poem titled "The Mill in Its Turn" in the journal "Mushtum", signaling a shift or evolution in his perspective during the new era of Ramadan.

**Ishchi yutdi, boylar yutqazdi-ku,
Oktabr oyi bizni qutqazdi-ku!..[2: 186]
Siz uchun erdi Xudodek Nekolay,
Qoyil o'ldingizmi, bir qulluq qilay...[2: 187]**

From these lines, it is evident that socio-historical conditions also influenced the shaping and evolution of the poet's poetic thought and aesthetic ideals.

"The October Song," published under the pseudonym "Magzhava" in the issue of the journal "Mushtum" dated November 7, 1925, serves as a clear representation of the changes in his creative work.

**O'ktabr, sen bizni ozod aylading,
Zanjirlarni uzib barbod aylading,
Kambag'allar ko'nglin ko'b shod aylading,
Obodonlig' o'zing bunyod aylading,
Qilsun tinmay boylar armon, O'ktabr!**

In terms of expression, weight, and theme, one can sense that he is now a creator of an entirely different direction, that he now views the world with a distinct perspective. He has transformed from Tavallo, the poet who extols "the ummah of the Beloved, our slave, our poor one," into a purposeful, ironic satirist, and publicist.

It is advisable to analyze how the introduction of newspapers and journals into the world, as well as the environment surrounding them, influenced Tavallo's creativity. For instance, "The Gazette of Turkestan," released in Tashkent in 1870, was not only the first example of printing in the local language but is also frequently noted in literary sources as a tool for Akposhshi propaganda. It is essential to note that, although the editors of the newspaper were Tatars, such as Sh. Ibrokhimov (1872), Kh. Chanishev (1881), and Uzbeks, such as I. Khudoyorkhanov (1893), the initial owner and manager was N. Ostroumov. Therefore, the newspaper could not be considered a pan-national publication [3: 209]. N. Ostroumov also instructed the majority of local creative individuals to produce works on topics favorable to the tsarist government, thus providing an opportunity for their publication. Active authors, following this "commission," received "permission" to express issues of everyday life through the "Turkestan Region Gazette." During this period, Tolagan Khodjamorov naturally did not miss the opportunity to contribute. From 1914 to 1916, more than 10 publicistic articles and six poems were published in the "Turkestan Region Gazette."

"The newspaper aimed to publish more works dedicated to various aspects of Turkestan's everyday life," writes A. Jalolov. However, it is interesting that the newspaper did not print all works that cast a "stain" on Russia, the "white prince," its policies, the Russian authorities in Turkestan, and that tarnished their reputation. Through a thorough analysis of the "Vestnik Turkestanskogo Kraya," we have ascertained that on its pages, there was neither an article nor a poem, nor any material, nor even a small amount of information directed against Russia or its colonial policy in Turkestan, or even hinted at it. "We did not find anything of the sort published" [4: 23-24]. In the run-up to the first bourgeois revolution, its literary content expanded somewhat, with more articles and poems related to education, science, and literary arts being published. There were specific reasons for this. First and foremost, N. P. Ostroumov gathered the Turkestan intelligentsia around him and aimed to take control of the "reins of governance." Secondly, through them, they sought to more widely propagate Russian policy in Turkestan. Thirdly, he tried to increase the popularity of the newspaper among the people. During the years of the First World War, the direction of newspapers and journals published in Turkestan changed. The theme of the war became part of the periodical press and literature of that time. N. Ostroumov issued "commissions" to Uzbek artists to

write works expressing desires for Russia's victory, praising and glorifying the "white horse."

As a result, a series of "commissioned" poems emerged in Uzbek literature. The artistic quality of the "Ordered" works was extremely low, and they largely constituted a collection of simple, rhyming words.

Poets who wrote such verses, firstly, found themselves too emotional and distant from artistic merit because they composed on a subject poorly known to them. Secondly, since the creators wrote these "orders" against their will, they were produced without inspiration.

From the pulpit of speaking to the nation

Kel, Tavallo, sen haqiqat so'zni yoz, yoshurmay hech,

Zoye' o'lmas millata har qancha xidmatlar darig'[5],

The poet who could articulate such slogans concluded his dedicatory verses with demands that reflected the social, political, and historical conditions of the time. While the imperial government was recruiting young individuals from the local population for work in the rear, Tavallo also wrote a series of poems urging Turkestanis to take up employment. We believe that such lines are a product of the prevailing socio-historical conditions in Turkestan and the mindset of the artist of that time. This is because, like everyone else, the creator can arrive at truth through debates, uncertainties, and discoveries, and in this process, he may take an unexpected, human path. In the testimonial materials related to the "case of Tolagan Khodjamorov," archived under SSS (State Security Service) number 32592, it is recorded that Tavallo, during one of the gatherings, stated: "The Uzbek people fell into 'red' slavery because of their disunity and cowardice" and remained in a disgraceful position... If the revolution brought us to such a state, if I had known, I would have fought against it with my head..." - he said. This quote further corroborates the viewpoint presented earlier.

The fact that the content of Tavallo's works changed over time can be explained by historical and political conditions, shifts in worldview, and the discovery of truth.

In the early years of his artistic career, Tavallo experimented with classical genres of Eastern poetry; however, the theme of "divine love" or "metaphorical love" was not a predominant feature in his works. Therefore, Tavallo's works were almost never mentioned in the creation of bayts, which took on a traditional form in the late 19th to early 20th century (with the exception of the

bayt "Sabzazor," containing instructional verses). This is apt to interpret not as a doubt in his talent but rather as a circumstance related to the theme of Bayoza's.

The compilation of Tavallo's works began with the collection "Sabzazor," compiled in 1914. Two years later, the poet assembled and published his poems under the title "Ravnak ul-Islam." The influence of socio-historical events on Tavallo's creativity is evident from the content of this collection, with the majority of its poems dedicated to specific events. Specifically, 31 of them focus on the nation and people; there are 7 poems on educational and school themes, 5 poems about time and related news, 8 poems dedicated to the press and theater, 3 works urging development, 2 poems on religious themes, and 3 laments. There are also works written about freedom, homeland, weddings and mourning, and trade.

Tavallo, active both in public life and the literary process, expressed his approach to each event through poems and articles in the pages of periodicals. In other words, changes over time prompted him to engage with new themes. Especially in the years 1914–1917, Tavallo was prolific. Newspapers such as "Tardjumon," "Vedomosti Turkestanskoi Oblasti," "Sadoi Turkestan," "Sadoyi Fergana," "Samarkand," "Nadzhot," and magazines like "Oyna," "Al-Islah," "Al-Izah" under the pseudonym Tolagan Khodjamorov published controversial articles and artistic samples. From 1924 to 1930, he became an active contributor to the journal "Mushtum."

From his biographical information, it is evident that Tavallo intensified his activities from the year 1913. This may be a result of his creative collaboration with new publications in the domestic press.

Analyzing the socio-historical foundations of the evolution of the poetic image in Tavallo's poetry, we directly attempted to understand "...various life and political factors that influenced the author, shaping his revered truths, sources that served as the occasion and material for writing the work, and the logic of their interpretation" [6: 34].

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